

D6.2 DLT Architecture and Governance Model

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Contributing Author(s)	Alfredo Favenza, LINKS Alessandro Mozzato, LINKS Silvio Meneguzzo, LINKS		
Reviewer(s)	Georgios Barzegkar-Ntovom, UBITECH Energy Lorenzo Solida, POLITO Pietro Colella, POLITO Ettore Bompard, POLITO Tao Huang, POLITO Marcelo Masera, POLITO Mahmood Hosseini, POLITO		

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List of abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
D	Deliverable
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DApps	Decentralized Applications
DC	Data Cellar
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technologies
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European
EVM	Ethereum Virtual Machine
IoT	Internet of Things
PoW	Proof of Work
PoS	Proof of Stake
PPoS	Pure Proof of Stake
PoH	Proof of History
RDBMS	Relational Data Base System
Rpc	Remote Procedure Call
T	Task
WP	Work Package
yr	year

Executive Summary

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D6.2 “DLT Architecture and Governance Model – First version” in the framework of the project titled “Data hub for the Creation of Energy Communities at Local Level and to Advance Research on them” (Project Acronym: DATA CELLAR, Grant Agreement No. 101069694) and provides a report on the activities of T6.2.

The main objective of D6.2 is to report the results of the activities performed in the scope of Task 6.2 “Interoperable, low energy consumption DLT layer” which aims at:

- Perform a benchmark of existing DLT-based data marketplaces.
- Analyse and select the DLT platforms that best fits the needs of DATA CELLAR in terms of functionalities, interoperability, scalability, decentralization, and security.
- Provide an architectural design of the DLT-based marketplace solution for DATA CELLAR.
- Implement a preliminary prototype of the DLT-based marketplace with limited functionalities.

In the second version of the Deliverable D6.3 - “DLT Architecture and Governance Model – Issue 2”, which will take place in month 36, an improved and final solution will be proposed regarding the implementation of the DLT Data Marketplace.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

A greener energy system is crucial for the future prosperity and liveability of European citizens. This requirement is at the heart of the DATA CELLAR approach where Local Energy Communities (LECs) have been recognised by the European Commission as a pivotal measure to play a key role in driving the EU's energy transition. At the same time, the digitisation of the EU energy system and the proper exchange of data between energy actors appear crucial to foster the exchange of best practices and the creation of a knowledge community to tackle one of our society's most pressing global crises: climate change.

Figure 1: DATA CELLAR Rationale

In this context, DATA CELLAR aims to implement a collaborative platform that will provide an interoperable, and secure energy data space capable of delivering access to datasets and AI models to serve and support the spread of energy communities in the European Union, leveraging on experience gained in the development of other EU projects.

DATA CELLAR will create a decentralized data space to store streams or historical data coming from private metering, but it will also provide a data federation integrating data coming from both external companies and EU federation spaces. The data space will be populated by a series of services dedicated to energy utilities, energy communities, private businesses, and citizens. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will provide a decentralized and open marketplace for energy datasets and pre-trained AI models to serve and support LECs.

To achieve its objectives, DATA CELLAR is divided into 9 WPs with different objectives, tasks, and deliverables. WP6 aims to design and develop a decentralized and open marketplace for energy datasets and AI models leveraging Distributed Ledger Technologies for data validation, tokenization and valorisation.

1.2. Deliverable scope and objectives

The objective of this report is to document the activities performed in the scope of Task 6.2 “Interoperable, low energy consumption DLT layer”. The main goals of T6.2 is to choose which Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) platform best fits the needs of DATA CELLAR in terms of data scalability and security while providing a decentralized and open marketplace for data and models.

The first part of the report aims to present the result of a detailed benchmark analysis of existing Data Marketplace solutions to select the target DLT platform which is more suitable for DATA CELLAR needs and requirements. Considering the needs of interoperability and federation for EU Energy Data Spaces, focusing on low energy consumption consensus algorithms (e.g., Proof-of-Stake, Proof-of-Authority, Federated Byzantine Agreement) for DLT operations and maintenance, both permissioned and permissionless blockchains alternatives in private/public data ownership infrastructure setups will be analysed (e.g., Ethereum 2.0, Hyperledger Fabric). The complete list of indicators taken into consideration for this benchmark is provided in the report.

The second part of this deliverable describes the architecture proposed for the DLT-based Marketplace of DATA CELLAR and the subset of architectural components and functionalities implemented, tested, and released for the very first prototype.

1.3. Deliverable structure

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 introduces the deliverable.
- Section 2 describes the list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) adopted for the Benchmark of different DLT target solutions.
- Section 3 describes the results of the Benchmark analysis.
- Section 4 describes the characteristic target DLT platform selected after the benchmarking.
- Section 5 describes the DATA CELLAR DLT-based Marketplace Architecture Design and its initial implementation in the preliminary prototype.

2. Definition of Data Marketplace Key Performance Indicators

In the process of developing a data marketplace, conducting a comprehensive analysis of existing data marketplaces becomes pivotal. This analysis aids in evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of these platforms, providing valuable insights that can shape the design and management of a new data marketplace. As we embark on the journey to create our own data marketplace, we have meticulously examined various data marketplaces to assess their performance, usability, and impact. This evaluation extends to the examination of KPIs, which play a critical role in understanding the dynamics and effectiveness of these platforms.

Understanding the KPIs of existing data marketplaces is paramount, as it equips us with the knowledge required to make informed and data-driven decisions in building our own platform. By closely scrutinizing these KPIs, we gain insights into user engagement, data quality, marketplace efficiency, and overall marketplace health.

In the following section, we will outline the primary KPIs we have examined during our assessment of data marketplaces. These KPIs will serve as foundational benchmarks, aligning our objectives and strategies with industry best practices and user expectations.

2.1. Service type

It refers to the different delivery models or data access modes offered by the platform. These models determine to whom the data marketplace services are directed and how data exchange takes place. Here is an explanation of the three main service types:

- **B2B (Business-to-Business):** In a B2B service model within a data marketplace, data is exchanged between businesses or organizations. In this case, companies use the data marketplace to acquire data that can be useful for improving their business operations, making strategic decisions, or enriching their product or service offerings. For example, a market research company might purchase demographic data from a B2B data marketplace to enhance their market research efforts.
- **B2C (Business-to-Consumer):** In a B2C service model, data is offered directly to end consumers. These consumers can be individual consumers or users seeking data for personal purposes, such as research, analysis, or to support their own decisions. For instance, an individual might use a B2C data marketplace to purchase weather-related data for planning their outdoor activities.
- **M2M (Machine-to-Machine):** The M2M service model involves the automatic exchange of data between machines or devices without human intervention. This type of service is often used in IoT (Internet of Things) scenarios, where sensors, devices, and automated systems collect data and share it with each other or with other control systems. For example, environmental

monitoring sensors in an industrial area might automatically share data about environmental conditions with other control systems.

The choice of service type in a data marketplace depends on the target audience, the purpose of data exchange, and the industry in which the marketplace operates. These service models define how data is offered, who can access it and for what purposes, helping to outline the role and value of the data marketplace within the business or technological ecosystem it serves.

2.2. Data type

It refers to the content of the data available on a data marketplace. This aspect is crucial as it defines what the data represents and how it can be useful to users. Here is a more detailed explanation:

- **What the data represents:** Data can encompass a wide range of information. It can pertain to demographic data, such as age, gender, income, and location, financial data like stock prices, banking transactions, or economic forecasts, geospatial data such as maps, GPS coordinates, or tracking data, consumer data like shopping habits, meteorological data including temperature, humidity, and weather forecasts, industry-related data like production and inventory, scientific data such as experimental results or research data, and many other types of information.
- **Fields of interest:** Data can be categorized based on fields of interest. For example, it can be oriented toward healthcare, finance, agriculture, environmental, energy, transportation, entertainment, or any other specific sector. This helps users easily identify data relevant to their specific needs.
- **Data source:** It can also indicate the source of the data. This can be particularly important in determining the credibility and reliability of the data. For example, data can originate from official sources, IoT sensors, academic research studies, or user contributions.

2.3. Data domain

The Data domain plays a crucial role in determining the diversity of data types available on the marketplace. Data marketplaces, according to this specific KPI, can be of two types:

- **Specific:**
 - **Focus on a sector:** A "data domain specific" data marketplace specializes in a particular sector or domain. This means it primarily offers data relevant to a specific industry, such as healthcare, automotive, agriculture, environmental sciences, and so on.
 - **Specialized Users:** These data marketplaces cater to users operating within that specific sector. For example, a healthcare-specific data marketplace would provide data relevant to medical professionals, researchers, or healthcare industry companies.

- **High Specialization:** Because they focus on a specific domain, such marketplaces can provide highly specialized and detailed data. This can be essential for users requiring refined information in their field.
- **Unspecific:**
 - **Wide Range of Sectors:** A "data domain unspecific" data marketplace offers a broad range of data that is not tied to a specific sector or domain. This data can cover various industries, such as finance, weather, demographics, geospatial, and many others.
 - **Diverse Users:** These marketplaces are designed for users with diverse needs. Buyers and sellers may come from a wide array of sectors and disciplines.
 - **Flexibility:** Since they are not restricted to a single domain, "data domain unspecific" data marketplaces are flexible and can adapt to a broader audience's needs, allowing users to explore and access data from various categories.

2.4. AI/service models exchange

Indicates whether in a data marketplace, in addition to the possibility of buying and selling data, it is also possible to sell or buy services.

2.5. AI/service models type

If it is possible to buy or sell services within a data marketplace, this KPI provides us with a description of the type of services that can be sold or purchased.

2.6. Ways to use Services

AI services made available through marketplaces can be used by users in various ways, depending on the nature of the service and the platforms involved. Here is how it generally works:

- **Online Access:** Many AI services can be used directly through a web interface. Users can access these services through a web browser without having to download or install anything locally. This approach is convenient and accessible from any device with an internet connection.
- **API Integration:** Some AI services offer APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) that allow developers to integrate AI capabilities directly into their own applications or services. This provides greater flexibility for custom implementation.

- **Download and Installation:** In the case of AI software, users can download the AI software or package from the marketplace and install it locally on their devices. After installation, users can use the service offline or online, depending on the application's specific requirements.
- **Licenses or Activation Keys:** Some AI services require the purchase of licenses or activation keys. Once purchased, these keys or licenses are used to unlock or activate the service or software. This method is common for AI software and video games.
- **Cloud Hosting:** Some AI services are hosted on cloud infrastructure and can be accessed through an API, a web interface, or a dedicated mobile application. Users access these services using an account or a specific interface provided by the cloud service provider.
- **AI Platforms:** Some AI platforms offer a complete environment for AI model development, training, and deployment. Users can access these platforms through a web interface or API to create, train, and deploy their own AI models.

2.7. Marketplace type

Marketplace type characteristics reveal information regarding the platform's autonomy. It distinguishes between two possibilities concerning data marketplaces:

- **Data Marketplaces Run by Data Providers (Platform&Services):** In this scenario, the data marketplace is operated by the same entities that are actively engaged in direct data trading, known as data providers. These data providers often have a vested interest in the data being transacted on their platform, as they are both suppliers and potential buyers. This setup is commonly seen among large companies, especially those with substantial data assets. These companies choose to operate their own data platforms to facilitate regular data exchanges with external parties. By doing so, they maintain a higher degree of control over their data assets and can tailor the marketplace to their specific needs. This approach provides a more customized and direct experience for data transactions.
- **Neutral Marketplace Operators (Only Platform):** In contrast, neutral marketplace operators are entities that do not have a stake in the data being traded. They remain impartial and do not align themselves with either the supplier or the buyer side. Neutral marketplaces provide a level playing field for data exchange, where businesses of all sizes and types can participate. Smaller companies often prefer to use these neutral platforms to facilitate data exchange. By doing so, they can access a wide range of data sources without being tied to a specific provider. Neutral marketplaces promote transparency and fairness in the data marketplace, making it easier for different players to engage in data transactions without favouring any specific party.

2.8. Marketplace access

The degree of openness of a platform is a critical factor defined by the concept of market access. This concept plays a pivotal role in shaping the dynamics of marketplaces. It categorizes marketplaces into three primary models: closed, open, and mixed forms, each with distinct characteristics and implications.

- **Closed Marketplaces:** Closed marketplaces exhibit a high level of control over their platform. They strictly regulate access, limiting it to a select group of trusted partners. This controlled environment allows for a high degree of quality assurance, as participants are carefully vetted and often have well-established relationships. Closed marketplaces are characterized by their exclusivity and may be suitable for scenarios where data security and quality control are of paramount importance. However, the downside is a limited pool of participants, potentially constraining the scope and scale of data exchange.
- **Open Marketplaces:** In contrast, open marketplaces adopt a more inclusive approach. They are designed to cater to a broad and often unknown group of participants. This inclusivity creates a larger target audience, thereby increasing the activities on the platform. However, this openness comes at the cost of reduced control over the quality and usage of the data products available on the marketplace. With a diverse range of participants, quality assurance can be challenging, and there is a need for robust mechanisms to ensure data integrity and security.
- **Mixed Forms:** Some marketplaces opt for a hybrid approach. These mixed forms combine elements of both closed and open models. They facilitate controlled and regulated exchange between selected actors, often with established partnerships. Simultaneously, they open a portion of their platform to newcomers, albeit subject to specific requirements or criteria. This approach seeks to strike a balance between the advantages of exclusivity and the benefits of a broader participant base. It provides flexibility and allows for controlled expansion while maintaining a degree of quality control.

2.9. Data transformation

The concept of data transformation plays a pivotal role in distinguishing the quality and usability of data within a marketplace. It encompasses several stages of processing and preparation that range from minimal intervention to comprehensive enhancement. These stages are essential in shaping the value-added services offered within the realm of data trading.

- **Raw Data Trading:** In its most unaltered form, data trading involves minimal data transformation. This means that data packages or data streams are exchanged in their raw, unprocessed state. This approach is characterized by its simplicity, as the primary function of the marketplace is to facilitate the transmission of data without any syntactic or semantic checks. The value-added services in raw data trading are confined to the fundamental act of forwarding data as it is received.

- **Data Normalization:** Data normalization is the next level of data transformation. During normalization, data undergoes a process of comparison against standardized data models. This comparison serves to identify discrepancies and variations in data formats, and the data is then converted into a uniform syntactic format. This step ensures that the data, regardless of its source, adheres to a consistent structure, making it more accessible and interoperable.
- **Data Aggregation:** Data aggregation takes the transformation a step further by collecting data in a structured, aggregated format. The marketplace operator compiles data into logical packages, often organized in reports or datasets. This preparation results in combined data sets that are ready for further analysis. Data aggregation simplifies the data presentation and enhances its usability for data consumers, reducing the need for extensive post-processing.
- **Quality Assurance:** Quality assurance is a critical aspect of data transformation, guaranteeing the high or constant quality of data traded on the marketplace. This is achieved through a series of consistency and quality checks. These checks help identify and rectify errors, inconsistencies, or anomalies within the data. Quality assurance processes aim to maintain the integrity and reliability of data, ensuring that it meets the expected standards for usability and accuracy.

2.10. Price models

The price model, within the context of data marketplaces, plays a pivotal role in determining how the final cost is structured for data buyers acquiring data products. It encompasses a range of variants, each designed to cater to different needs and scenarios, thereby providing flexibility and options for both data providers and consumers.

- **Free Data Access:** One of the primary variants is where data from public authorities or non-profit organizations is made available free of charge. This approach serves as a valuable incentive to attract new users to the data marketplace. By offering data at no cost, the platform can encourage broader participation and generate interest from a diverse user base.
- **Fixed-Price or Subscription Model:** In the fixed-price or subscription model, data is offered for access over a specific period. Users pay a predetermined fee for the right to access and use the data within the defined timeframe. This model ensures predictability in costs and often suits scenarios where regular or extended access to data is required.
- **Package Pricing:** Another approach involves package pricing, wherein various packages with different features and usage limits are made available at fixed prices. Larger packages may be more expensive, but they offer a lower per-unit cost, making them cost-effective for users with greater data needs. This pricing strategy allows users to choose packages that align with their specific requirements.
- **Pay-Per-Use Model:** The pay-per-use model charges users based on the actual consumption of data. It sets a price for each unit of data consumed, and the final cost is determined by the

volume of data utilized. This approach is especially suitable for those who require data sporadically or in variable quantities, as it ensures that users pay only for what they use.

- **Progressive Pricing:** Progressive pricing is based on the demand for data products. As more customers purchase licenses to access a specific dataset, the price increases accordingly. This model is strategically employed when there is a need to control or restrict the dissemination of data products. It incentivizes early adopters while generating revenue as demand grows. The pricing structure evolves as more users express interest, reflecting the market's dynamics.

2.11. Marketplace revenue model

The revenue model, in the context of data marketplaces, is a fundamental aspect that outlines how the marketplace operator generates revenue. It provides insights into the specific strategies employed to monetize the services and resources offered by the marketplace. Various approaches and patterns of turnover generation are adopted by data marketplaces, allowing for flexibility and customization based on the marketplace's goals and the nature of the data being exchanged.

- **Transaction Commission:** One of the most common revenue models involves calculating a commission for each data transaction facilitated by the marketplace. In this model, a percentage of the transaction value or a fixed fee is charged to the data buyer and/or seller for using the marketplace as an intermediary. This commission-based approach aligns revenue generation with the actual exchange of data, making it a performance-driven model.
- **Membership and Listing Fees:** Data marketplaces may also charge fees for membership or for listing data products. Users, both data providers and consumers, pay a fee to join the marketplace, and additional fees may apply for listing data products. These fees contribute to the overall revenue stream of the platform and help support its operational costs.
- **Storage Space and Data Services Fees:** Some data marketplaces offer storage space for data products or provide additional data-related services, such as data analytics or data processing. In such cases, fees are charged based on the storage capacity utilized or the services availed. This revenue model aligns costs with the usage of platform resources and services.
- **Freemium Model:** The Freemium revenue model offers a tiered approach to pricing. Users can access basic platform functions for free, while an extended or full range of features requires a paid subscription or a one-time fee. This model balances accessibility with premium services, allowing users to choose the level of functionality that suits their needs.
- **Flat Rate Tariff:** In the flat rate tariff model, customers pay a fixed lump sum, typically on a regular basis (e.g., monthly or annually), regardless of the scope of their service usage. This approach offers simplicity and predictability in pricing and is often chosen by users who require consistent and continuous access to the marketplace's offerings.

- **Free and Open Access:** Some data marketplaces, particularly those operated by public authorities and non-profit organizations, make their platforms available entirely free of charge and without restrictions. These marketplaces prioritize accessibility and public benefit over revenue generation. They may be funded by public funds or grants and aim to provide valuable data resources to the community at no cost.

2.12. Sustainability over time

It is platform's ability to remain active, efficient, and relevant in the long run. This concept is important because many platforms, especially those based on emerging technologies like blockchain, need to demonstrate their ability to adapt, grow, and maintain their value over time. Sustainability over time for a Data Marketplace can encompass several metrics:

- **Project Longevity:** A sustainable Data Marketplace should have a history of prolonged activity, with years of continuous operation without significant interruptions. Project longevity can be an indicator of reliability.
- **Continuous Updates:** The platform should demonstrate a commitment to continuously updating and improving its infrastructure and offered features. This ensures that the platform keeps pace with new technologies and user needs over time.
- **Active Usage:** Sustainability can be reflected in user activity and the volume of data exchanged on the platform. A platform with consistent usage over time is more sustainable than one that loses interest.
- **Active Community:** An active community of users and developers can significantly contribute to the sustainability of a Data Marketplace. An engaged community can help solve issues, develop new features, and promote the platform.
- **Service Diversification:** A sustainable platform should be capable of diversifying the services offered over time. For example, it might initially offer only one type of dataset and then expand to cover a wider range of applications or services.

2.13. DLT accessibility

DLT is a fundamental component of a decentralized marketplace, as it manages, and records transactions and information related to business activities on the platform. There are different ways of accessibility to the DLT, each with unique characteristics and suitability for specific use cases. Below, an introduction to the main types of DLT that a decentralized marketplace could use is provided:

- **Public Blockchain:** Public blockchains are decentralized and open to anyone who wants to participate. They are known for their immutability and transparency, as transactions are recorded on a global network and validated by a distributed node community. This technology is ideal for marketplaces that require high transparency and security, such as cryptocurrency markets.

- **Private Blockchain:** In contrast, private blockchains are controlled by a limited group of authorized participants. This type of DLT is suitable for enterprise marketplaces where privacy and control are a priority. Transactions are generally faster than in public blockchains but sacrifice some decentralization and transparency.
- **Hybrid Blockchain:** Hybrid blockchains combine elements of public and private blockchains, allowing for greater flexibility in balancing security, control, and public access. This model is suitable for situations where a compromise between privacy and transparency is needed.
- **Permissioned Blockchain:** Permissioned blockchains require participant identification and authorization. They are useful for marketplaces that want to control who can access and participate in transactions while providing greater efficiency compared to public blockchains.

2.14. DLT type

This field indicates the technology used by a specific data marketplace. There are numerous DLTs on which it is possible to build a decentralised platform for the exchange of data and services, the most used and important ones are listed below:

- **Bitcoin:** the first and most well-known cryptocurrency. It uses a blockchain as a distributed ledger to record and verify transactions. Its main feature is the Proof of Work (PoW) consensus algorithm.
- **Ethereum:** It is a blockchain platform that supports the development of smart contracts. In contrast to Bitcoin, Ethereum uses the Proof of Stake (PoS) consensus algorithm and is at the center of a decentralized applications (DApps) ecosystem.
- **Algorand:** It is a blockchain that aims to improve scalability and transaction speed. It utilizes a consensus model called Pure Proof of Stake (PPoS) and aims to enable high throughput without compromising security.
- **Solana:** It is a blockchain designed for scalability, offering very high transaction speeds. It uses a Proof of History (PoH) approach combined with Proof of Stake (PoS) to ensure efficiency and security.
- **IOTA:** It is a blockchain without blocks and fees, focused on the IoT. It utilizes Tangle technology, a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), to handle transactions and achieve the scalability needed for IoT.

2.15. Transaction speed

Transaction speed measures the time required to process and successfully execute a transaction within the data marketplace. This KPI considers how quickly data purchase, sale, or exchange requests are fulfilled. Faster transaction speed is advantageous as it reduces waiting times and enhances the user experience. Transaction speed is crucial to ensure the efficiency and attractiveness of a data marketplace. Users desire their transactions to be executed promptly, especially in contexts where

timeliness is essential, such as in financial markets or real-time data acquisition. Good transaction speed increases user confidence in the platform. We can identify the following metrics for this specific property:

- **Average Transaction Confirmation Time (s/transaction):** It indicates the average time required to confirm and complete a transaction within the data marketplace. It is measured from the submission of the request to its confirmation. A shorter transaction confirmation time is preferable, as it reduces user wait times and allows them to conduct operations more quickly.
- **Average Request Execution Time (s/transaction):** It represents the average time required to successfully execute a transaction or service request on the platform. The average request execution time is crucial for measuring the operational efficiency of the platform. Reducing this time can significantly improve the user experience.
- **Platform Scalability:** It evaluates the platform's ability to handle a growing number of concurrent transactions without experiencing slowdowns or service interruptions. Scalability is essential to ensure that the platform can support an increasing volume of users and transactions without compromising transaction speed.

2.16. Transaction costs

Transaction costs represent the financial expenses associated with conducting operations within a data marketplace. These costs can vary depending on the type of transaction and the activities involved in the data exchange process. Costs may include transaction fees, access fees, validation fees, and other charges related to data purchase, sale, or usage on the platform. Transaction costs are a critical indicator as they directly impact the attractiveness of the data marketplace for both data providers and buyers. The expenses and commissions incurred can influence users' decisions to participate in the platform and play a significant role in determining the overall profitability of the marketplace. We can identify the following metrics for this specific property:

- **Average Fee Rate (USD/transaction):** This metric represents the average fees applied per transaction within the data marketplace. It can be expressed as a percentage of the transaction value or as a fixed fee. The average fee rate directly impacts the costs incurred by users during transactions. A higher rate may discourage marketplace usage, while lower fees can make it more attractive.
- **Average Cost per Transaction (USD/transaction):** This metric calculates the average cost incurred by users for each transaction on the platform. It includes transaction fees, access fees, and other charges. The average cost per transaction provides a clear view of the actual expenses incurred by users when using the data marketplace. Minimizing it can make the platform more competitive.
- **Total Annual Expenses (USD):** This metric represents the total sum of annual expenses incurred by all users on the platform. It includes transaction fees and other fees. Total annual

expenses offer insight into the overall volume of costs generated on the platform over a specific period. This data can be useful for evaluating the marketplace's profitability.

- **Fee Structure:** This metric refers to the specific configuration of transaction fees on the platform. It may include fixed fees, variable fees based on the transaction amount, volume-based discounts, or other special fees. Understanding the fee structure is essential for assessing how transaction costs may vary based on different factors. A clear and fair fee structure can positively influence marketplace usage.

2.17. KPI summary table

The table below lists the KPIs just outlined in a summarised manner. In addition, we will find a column indicating the rating of each one.

More specifically, we will have a three-level division according to how a certain data marketplace responds to a KPI:

- High: indicates that the data marketplace responds very well to what our implementation requires.
- Medium: indicates that the data marketplace responds sufficiently to what our implementation requires.
- Low: the data marketplace presents characteristics that do not exactly coincide with our implementation needs.

In some cases, the medium value will not be presented as the evaluation choice will be binary.

KPI	Type	Summary	Evaluation
Service Type	Qualitative	It refers to the different delivery models or data access modes offered by the platform. These models determine to whom the data marketplace services are directed and how data exchange takes place.	High: B2B and B2C Medium: B2B or B2C Low: M2M
Data Type	Qualitative	It refers to the content of the data available on a data marketplace. This aspect is crucial as it defines what the data represents and how it can be useful to users.	The more diverse, the better.
Data Domain	Qualitative	The Data domain plays a crucial role in determining the diversity of data types available on the marketplace. Data provided are of a specific type or of generical type.	High: Unspecific Low: Specific
AI/service models exchange	Qualitative	Indicates whether in a data marketplace, in addition to the possibility of buying and selling data, it is also possible to sell or buy services.	High: Yes Low: No
AI/service models type	Qualitative	Description of the type of services that can be sold or purchased.	The more diverse, the better.
Ways to use Services	Qualitative	AI services made available through marketplaces can be used by users in various ways, depending on the	The more diverse, the better.

		nature of the service and the platforms involved.	
Marketplace type	Qualitative	Marketplace type characteristics reveal information regarding the platform's autonomy. It can be Neutral or act like a Provider.	High: Neutral Low: Provider
Marketplace access	Qualitative	The degree of openness of a platform is a critical factor defined by the concept of market access. This concept plays a pivotal role in shaping the dynamics of marketplaces. It categorizes marketplaces into three primary models: closed, open, and mixed forms, each with distinct characteristics and implications.	High: Closed Medium: Mixed Low: Open
Data transformation	Qualitative	It distinguishes the quality and usability of data within a marketplace. It encompasses several stages of processing and preparation that range from minimal intervention to comprehensive enhancement.	High: Quality ass. Medium: Data transf. Low: Other
Price models	Qualitative	It determines how the final cost is structured for data buyers acquiring data products. It encompasses a range of variants, each designed to cater to different needs and scenarios.	The more diverse, the better.
Marketplace revenue models	Qualitative	It outlines how the marketplace operator generates revenue. It provides insights into the specific strategies employed to monetize the services and resources offered by the marketplace.	High: Transaction fees Low: Other
Sustainability over time	Qualitative	It is platform's ability to remain active, efficient, and relevant in the long run.	The higher the better
DLT accessibility	Qualitative	It manages, and records transactions and information related to business activities on the platform: Public, Private, Hybrid, Permissioned.	High: Private Medium: Hybrid Low: Other
DLT type	Qualitative	This field indicates the technology used by a specific data marketplace. There are numerous DLTs on which it is possible to build a decentralised platform for the exchange of data and services.	High: EVM (Ethereum Virtual Machine) compatible Low: Other
Transaction speed	Quantitative/ Qualitative	Transaction speed measures the time required to process and successfully execute a transaction within the data marketplace.	The higher the better
Transaction costs	Quantitative/ Qualitative	Transaction costs represent the financial expenses associated with conducting operations within a data marketplace.	The lower the better

Table 1. KPIs Summary table

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3. Data Marketplace Benchmark

Following extensive research and desk analysis, we have considered the following data marketplaces platforms and solutions as the best known and most widely used. We have distinguished between blockchain-based and non-blockchain-based marketplaces by evaluating each one according to the KPIs presented in the previous section.

Legend	
●	Indicates that the item possesses full capabilities in the specified KPI.
◐	Signifies partial capabilities in the specified KPI, meaning there are some but not all features or functionalities available
○	Represents no capabilities in the specified KPI

	Service type	Data type	Data domain	AI models exchange	AI models type	Service access	Marketplace type	Marketplace access	Data transformation	Price models	Revenue model	Sustainability over time	DLT accessibility	DLT type	Transaction speed	Transaction cost
Ocean Protocol	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	◐	●	●	●	●	◐	●	◐	●
Datum	●	●	●	○	○	○	●	◐	◐	●	●	○	◐	●	◐	●
DataWallet	●	◐	●	○	○	○	●	◐	◐	◐	●	◐	◐	◐	◐	◐
Fysical	○	◐	◐	○	○	○	●	◐	◐	◐	◐	○	◐	◐	◐	◐
Dawex	●	●	●	●	◐	◐	●	◐	○	◐	◐	●	●	◐	◐	◐
Streamr	○	◐	●	●	◐	◐	●	◐	●	◐	n/a	●	◐	◐	●	●
Zenodys	●	●	◐	○	○	○	●	◐	●	◐	◐	○	◐	◐	◐	◐
IOTA	○	◐	◐	○	○	○	●	◐	○	◐	●	◐	●	◐	○	○
Databroker DAO	●	●	◐	◐	◐	◐	●	◐	○	◐	n/a	◐	◐	◐	◐	◐

Caruso Dataplace	●	●	◐	○	○	○	●	◐	●	●	◐	n/a	○	○	n/a	n/a
Advaneo	●	●	●	○	○	○	●	◐	○	◐	●	n/a	○	○	n/a	n/a
Otonomo	●	●	◐	○	○	○	●	◐	●	◐	●	n/a	○	○	n/a	n/a
InfoChimps	●	●	●	○	○	○	●	◐	○	◐	●	n/a	○	○	n/a	n/a
Qlik	●	●	●	○	○	○	○	◐	○	●	◐	●	○	○	n/a	n/a
Azure Data Marketplace	●	●	●	●	●	◐	●	◐	○	◐	●	●	○	○	n/a	n/a
Here OLP	●	◐	◐	●	◐	◐	○	◐	●	●	◐	●	○	○	n/a	n/a
Data Intelligence Hub	●	●	●	●	●	◐	●	◐	○	●	●	◐	○	○	n/a	n/a

Table 1. Data Marketplace Benchmark Analysis

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4. DLT platform selection

Following the analysis conducted in the previous chapter comparing all currently active data marketplaces and filtering by the DLT-based platforms, we found the best approach is the mixed use of GoQuorum, as private network based on Ethereum, and Ocean Protocol for the smart contract libraries that optimize data exchange following a GAIA-X compliant approach.

To be more specific, here are a number of detailed reasons for the choice just proposed:

- **Reliability and security of the private blockchain:** GoQuorum is an enterprise version of Ethereum that offers advanced security and privacy functionalities. By using a private blockchain, it's possible to control data access and ensure transaction security, ensuring that only authorized parties have access to sensitive information.
- **Scalability and transaction management:** GoQuorum is designed to handle a high number of transactions per second (TPS), enabling efficient scalability of the system. This is particularly crucial in a data marketplace where multiple transactions can occur simultaneously.
- **Superior KPI Performance Results:** Through our benchmarking across various data marketplace solutions, Ocean Protocol has demonstrated superior performance compared to others in meeting the analyzed Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Specifically, it has shown better efficiency in average transaction confirmation time, greater scalability to handle an increasing volume of simultaneous transactions, and a fee structure that aligns more favorably with user needs, reducing transaction costs. Its ability to integrate and facilitate process automation through smart contracts has significantly enhanced transparency, reliability, and overall effectiveness of our data marketplace. These results showcase Ocean Protocol's suitability as a key solution for building a successful data marketplace.
- **Integration of Ocean Protocol:** Integrating Ocean Protocol for smart contract-based logic offers a robust framework for data sharing management. Ocean Protocol provides an infrastructure for data sharing and control, allowing developers to create and implement specific smart contracts for data management within the marketplace.
- **Automation and transparency:** Smart contracts based on Ocean Protocol enable the automation of data transactions within the marketplace. This ensures transparency and reliability in the data exchange process, eliminating the need for intermediaries and reducing the risk of fraud or human errors.
- **Standardization and interoperability:** Ocean Protocol offers open standards and interoperable protocols that facilitate easier integration and collaboration with other platforms or services. This could ease expansion or collaboration with other entities in the data sector.
- **Community and support:** Both GoQuorum and Ocean Protocol are supported by active communities and dedicated developers. This can ensure regular updates, technical support, and a vast pool of shared knowledge that can be beneficial in creating and updating the data marketplace over time.

4.1. GoQuorum Ethereum Private Blockchain

Figure 2. GoQuorum Architecture

[GoQuorum](#) is a lightweight fork of [geth](#), which is a Go (Golang) programming language-based client software representing one of the primary implementations of the Ethereum protocol. In essence, Geth is a software node that enables participation in the Ethereum network and facilitates interaction with it. GoQuorum is updated as geth releases occur.

Thanks to Goquorum, it is possible to develop an own private consortium Ethereum blockchain to enable the decentralised management of information exchanged on the platform in a secure manner. All typical parameters of a blockchain can be customised as needed. Now, the value that these blockchain properties will have to take on has not yet been considered, but those can be listed on which specific decisions will have to be made according to the needs of the project:

- **Consensus Protocol:** Algorithm through which nodes reach the consensus on the Block released:
 - QBFT: The recommended enterprise-grade consensus protocol for private networks.
 - IBFT: Supported for existing private networks, but you can migrate a network using IBFT to QBFT.
 - Raft: Not recommended for production networks. You can migrate a network using Raft to another consensus protocol.
 - Clique: Not recommended for production networks. You can migrate a network using Clique to another consensus protocol.
- **Transaction Visibility:** Cryptographic keys are an essential component of a GoQuorum network. GoQuorum uses keys to create digital signatures which verify a sender's identity and prevent message tampering. The Privacy Manager uses keys to encrypt private transaction data. So, it is possible to decide to make them private or not.
- **Gas Network:** By default, GoQuorum is a free gas network, which means gas is priced at zero and is not consumed when transactions are processed. However, gas price can be enabled if

required. Transactions use computational resources, so they have associated costs. Gas is the cost unit and gas price is the price per gas unit. The transaction cost is the gas used multiplied by the gas price. If gas is enabled, then like public Ethereum networks, the account submitting the transaction pays the transaction cost, in Ether. The miner (or validator, in proof of authority networks) that includes the transaction in a block receives the transaction cost.

- **Network topology:** The Ethereum Blockchain network is based on the identification and definition of three fundamental types of nodes:
 - **Validator node:** It plays a central role in ensuring the security and integrity of the network. Its primary function is to validate transactions, a critical process that involves participating in consensus to ensure transactions are legitimate. After validation, the node contributes to adding new blocks to the blockchain, each containing a set of validated transactions. It is also responsible for maintaining the current state of the blockchain, including information such as account balances and the state of smart contracts. It is crucial for synchronization with other nodes in the network, ensuring a consistent view of the blockchain across all participants. Additionally, it participates in executing smart contracts through the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM). These nodes are vital for network security, participating in consensus processes like PoW or PoS depending on the blockchain's configuration. Validator node participation ensures resistance to attacks and network governance. In essence, the validator node represents a key factor in maintaining and evolving an Ethereum-based blockchain.
 - **Rpc (Remote procedure call) nodes:** They serve as a remote communication interface. Essentially, they act as a means through which applications or developers can interact with a blockchain node from an external location. In practice, they allow sending commands and obtaining information from the node without having to execute code locally. These nodes enable access to critical blockchain data, such as block information, transactions, account balances, and smart contract states. They can also perform operations on the blockchain, such as creating new transactions or executing smart contracts. Additionally, RPC nodes support digital wallets and user interfaces, enabling users to view and interact with their blockchain information. They can be customized based on specific needs, allowing users to request only the information they require, making the process more efficient.
 - **Bootstrap nodes:** they act as central "reference points" that new nodes can reach out to for information about the network and to be introduced to other nodes. This process significantly simplifies the initial discovery of nodes, especially for those joining the network for the first time. It facilitates the establishment of initial connections in the blockchain network by providing key information about other nodes and easing the initiation of synchronization. It is important to note that the number of bootstrap nodes is not necessarily limited and can vary based on the network configuration. Moreover, these nodes play a crucial role in maintaining the resilience and distribution of the network. They ensure that new participants can connect easily, contributing to the overall growth and decentralization of the network.

4.2. Ocean Protocol

[Ocean Protocol](#) functions as a gateway to data services within the realm of cryptocurrencies, offering a key to unlocking the intrinsic value of data. It harnesses the power of blockchain technology to establish connections between data providers and consumers. Data owners can harness the Ocean Market app to vend their data, effectively transforming it into a monetizable asset, all while maintaining strict control and privacy. On the flip side, consumers gain access to previously inaccessible private data.

This is particularly beneficial for artificial intelligence (AI) practitioners and data scientists who stand to profit from expanded data access, crypto-secured data provenance, and new income avenues. The concept of "compute-to-data" empowers the use of private data in AI models and research without the necessity of direct data sharing. Ocean Protocol users also have the potential to earn rewards by curating data through staking. Furthermore, developers have the flexibility to utilize Ocean Libraries to construct and launch their own decentralized marketplaces, wallets, and various applications.

The OCEAN token acts as the protocol's native utility token and is the default unit of exchange for acquiring and trading data on the Ocean Market. Additionally, it holds a pivotal role in governance and staking within the ecosystem.

The main strengths of using Ocean protocol as a reference marketplace from which to implement in DATA CELLAR are summarised below:

- **Interoperability and Open Standards:**
 - Benefits: Ocean Protocol is built on open standards, promoting interoperability across various platforms and ecosystems. This enables seamless integration with other blockchain projects, decentralized technologies, and traditional data systems.
 - Use Case: It is possible to create a data marketplace that can easily collaborate and interoperate with other decentralized applications or platforms.
- **Smart Contracts and Automation:**
 - Benefits: Smart contracts on Ocean Protocol automate key aspects of data exchange, such as pricing, access control, and payments. This reduces the need for intermediaries and ensures transparent and efficient transactions.
 - Use Case: It is possible to streamline and automate the data trading process, especially for microtransactions or complex contractual agreements.
- **Security and Privacy:**
 - Benefits: Ocean Protocol emphasizes data security through encryption and privacy-preserving techniques like "Compute-to-Data," allowing computations on encrypted data without exposing the raw information.
 - Use Case: For projects dealing with sensitive or personal data, or those requiring privacy-focused solutions, Ocean Protocol's security features offer a robust framework for handling and exchanging data.
- **Data Monetization:**
 - Benefits: Ocean Protocol provides tools for data providers to easily monetize their datasets. Users can set specific terms for accessing their data, including pricing and access conditions.

- Use Case: It is possible to create a data marketplace where users can monetize their data assets efficiently. Ocean Protocol's built-in features for setting and enforcing data monetization policies are advantageous.
- **Community and Ecosystem:**
 - Benefits: Ocean Protocol has an active and growing community of developers, data providers, and users. Leveraging this ecosystem can provide access to a network of expertise, collaborations, and potential users.
 - Use Case: If you value community support, collaborative opportunities, and a network effect for your data marketplace, Ocean Protocol's established community can be a valuable resource.
- **Flexibility:**
 - Benefits: Ocean Protocol is designed to be adaptable to various use cases and industries. Its flexibility allows customization to meet specific project requirements and business needs.
 - Use Case: If your data marketplace caters to diverse industries or has unique requirements, Ocean Protocol's flexibility provides the versatility needed for customization.
- **Scalability:**
 - Benefits: Ocean Protocol addresses scalability concerns through mechanisms like OceanDAO and Ocean Market, ensuring that the platform can handle increasing volumes of transactions and participants.
 - Use Case: For projects expecting significant growth or dealing with a large volume of data transactions, Ocean Protocol's scalability features contribute to the long-term viability of the data marketplace.

4.2.1. Ocean Protocol Architecture overview

In the figure below, we find the architecture of Ocean protocol. Starting from the bottom, we find the presence of four different layers, each interconnected to the one above it. We will therefore find the following layers in order, starting from the bottom, which we will analyse in the following sections:

- **Layer 1: The blockchain layer:** The part concerning the blockchain infrastructure and thus the smart contracts.
- **Layer 2: The Empowering Middle Layer:** Here we will find all the libraries that will allow the effective interaction with the blockchain layer and with the smart contracts.

- **Layer 3: The Accessible Application Layer:** Basically, here we find everything about the user interface, applications, and tools, inviting data scientists and curious explorers alike to access, explore, and contribute to the ocean's treasures.
- **Layer 4: The Friendly Wallets:** This is the component that allows us to assign a specific identity to the user who will then be able to interact in the marketplace.

Figure 3. Ocean Protocol Architecture

Layer 1

The Blockchain Layer

At the heart of Ocean Protocol is the resilient Blockchain Layer, underpinned by blockchain technology to guarantee secure and transparent transactions. This layer serves as the foundation of decentralized trust, where data providers and consumers converge to exchange valuable assets.

Smart contracts are deployed on the Ethereum Mainnet and other compatible networks. The libraries encapsulate interactions with these smart contracts, offering functionalities such as the publication of new assets, facilitating data consumption, managing pricing, and more.

Layer 2

The Empowering Middle Layer

Beyond the realm of smart contracts, you'll encounter a critical foundation consisting of libraries that form the backbone of the Ocean Protocol ecosystem, middleware components, and Compute-to-Data.

Ocean.js, a JavaScript library, and Ocean.py, a Python library, both serving as indispensable tools for developers, facilitating seamless integration and interaction with the protocol:

- **Ocean.js**, the JavaScript library, stands as a powerful resource for developers seeking to seamlessly integrate their applications into the Ocean Protocol ecosystem. Designed to simplify interactions with the protocol, Ocean.js offers a comprehensive range of functions, including data tokenization, asset management, and smart contract interaction. By streamlining the implementation of data access controls, the creation of DApps, and the exploration of datasets within a decentralized environment, Ocean.js empowers developers to unlock the full potential of the ecosystem.
- **Ocean.py**, the Python library, empowers developers to seamlessly integrate their applications with the Ocean Protocol ecosystem. With its extensive array of functionalities, Ocean.py provides a comprehensive toolkit for interacting with the protocol. Developers and data scientists can utilize Ocean.py for a wide spectrum of tasks, spanning from data tokenization and asset management to smart contract interactions. Serving as a bridge between Python and the decentralized realm of Ocean Protocol, this library facilitates the utilization of the transformative capabilities of decentralized data.

Furthermore, to support the discovery process, middleware components come into action:

- **Aquarius**: Aquarius serves as a metadata cache, elevating the efficiency of searches by caching on-chain data into Elasticsearch. This acceleration of metadata retrieval by Aquarius results in swifter and more effective data discovery processes.
- **Provider**: The Provider component assumes a pivotal role in facilitating various operations within the ecosystem. It aids in asset downloading, manages DDO (Decentralized Data Object) encryption, and establishes communication with the operator-service for Compute-to-Data jobs. This seamless coordination ensures secure and efficient interactions among various participants.
- **Subgraph**: The Subgraph operates as an off-chain service that utilizes GraphQL to provide efficient access to information related to datatokens, users, and balances. Leveraging the subgraph results in faster data retrieval compared to on-chain queries, enhancing the overall performance and responsiveness of applications that rely on accessing this information.

Compute-to-Data (C2D) heralds a transformative paradigm within the Ocean Protocol ecosystem, revolutionizing the data processing and analysis landscape. C2D disrupts the conventional data transfer model by prioritizing privacy and security. Instead of moving data to the computation, C2D securely transports algorithms to the data sources, allowing for local computation without exposing sensitive data. This innovative framework not only facilitates collaborative data analysis but also upholds stringent data privacy standards. It is particularly well-suited for scenarios where data owners seek to maintain control over their valuable assets. C2D serves as a potent tool for enabling secure and

privacy-preserving data analysis, fostering collaboration among data providers, and ensuring the efficient utilization of valuable data resources while maintaining robust privacy protocols.

Layer 3

The Accessible Application Layer

Here, the ocean teems with life, fostering a dynamic ecosystem of DApps, marketplaces, and more. This layer serves as a welcoming home to a plethora of user-friendly interfaces, applications, and tools, extending an open invitation to data scientists and inquisitive explorers, encouraging them to delve into the ocean's boundless treasures.

Taking center stage in this domain is Ocean Market, a bustling hub where data enthusiasts and industry stakeholders converge to uncover, trade, and unlock the inherent value of data assets. Beyond Ocean Market, the Application Layer harbors a diverse collection of specialized applications and marketplaces, each meticulously crafted to cater to unique use cases and industries. These applications, supercharged by the capabilities of Ocean Protocol, empower advanced data exploration, analytics, and collaborative endeavors, revolutionizing the landscape of data accessibility, sharing, and monetization.

Layer 4

The Friendly Wallets

At the summit of the Ocean Protocol ecosystem, we encounter the esteemed Web 3 Wallets, acting as the portal for users to immerse themselves in the realm of decentralized data transactions. These wallets stand as trusted companions, facilitating seamless transactions within the ecosystem, allowing users to procure and trade data NFTs, and acquire valuable datatokens.

4.2.2. Smart contracts overview

Figure 4. Ocean Protocol Smart Contracts

The suite of [smart contracts](#) (presented in Figure 4) forms the essential framework of the decentralized data economy. These contracts enable secure, transparent, and efficient interactions among data providers, consumers, and ecosystem participants.

Data NFTs for Data IP Management

In Ocean are adopted ERC721 tokens to explicitly represent the Data IP as "data NFTs" (Non-Fungible Tokens). In this way owners can deploy specific ERC20 "datatoken" contracts for their data NFTs, with each datatoken contract offering its own distinct licensing terms. Users can then purchase the specific datatokens related to a dataset (NFT) they want to have access to.

By utilizing ERC721 tokens, Ocean empowers data creators with greater flexibility and control over their licensing arrangements. The introduction of data NFTs allows for the representation of a variety of licensing options and the creation of customized ERC20 datatoken contracts tailored to individual licensing requirements.

Community monetization

Ocean opens enhanced opportunities for DApp owners, creating a conducive environment for the emergence of a thriving market of third-party providers.

With Ocean, dApp owners can unlock additional benefits. Firstly, smart contracts empower dApp owners to collect fees not only during data consumption but also through fixed-rate exchanges. This expanded revenue model allows owners to derive more value from the ecosystem. Moreover, in Ocean, the dApp operator has the authority to determine the fee value, providing them with increased control over their pricing strategies.

In addition to empowering dApp owners, Ocean facilitates the participation of third-party providers who can offer compute services in exchange for a fee. This paves the way for the development of a diverse marketplace of providers. This model supports both centralized trusted providers, where data publishers and consumers have established trust relationships, as well as trustless providers that leverage decentralization or other privacy-preserving mechanisms.

Ocean creates an ecosystem where various providers can offer their compute services, catering to the diverse needs of data publishers and consumers. Whether based on trust or privacy-preserving mechanisms, this expansion in provider options enhances the overall functionality and accessibility of the Ocean Protocol ecosystem.

Here explained some smart contracts features:

- Base IP represented by a data NFT, from which a data publisher can create multiple ERC20s datatokens representing different types of access for the same dataset.
- Interoperability with the NFT ecosystem (and DeFi & DAO tools).
- Allows new data NFT & datatoken templates, for flexibility and future-proofing.
- Besides base data IP, you can use data NFTs to implement comments & ratings, verifiable claims, identity credentials, and social media posts. They can point to parent data NFTs, enabling the nesting of comments on comments, or replies to tweets. All on-chain, GDPR-compliant, easily searched, with js & py drivers.
- Introduce an advanced Fee structure both for DApp and provider runners.
- Roles Administration: there are now multiple roles for a more flexible administration both at NFT and ERC20 levels.

- When the NFT is transferred, it auto-updates all permissions, e.g., who receives payment, or who can mint derivative ERC20 datatokens.
- Key-value store in the NFT contract: NFT contract can be used to store custom key-value pairs (ERC725Y standard) enabling applications like soulbound tokens and Sybil protection approaches.
- Multiple NFT template support: the Factory can deploy different types of NFT templates.
- Multiple datatoken template support: the Factory can deploy different types of datatoken templates.

4.2.3. Ocean Protocol peculiarities

Ocean Protocol employs its innovative datatokens to convert data into valuable assets, ushering in a host of advantages previously absent in the data market. This approach not only empowers data owners to monetize their data through tokenization but also democratizes data accessibility, making it available to anyone on the open market, including data that would typically be either unavailable or difficult to access.

The project places a significant emphasis on the enhancement of AI and the broad dissemination of its benefits. Data scientists can seamlessly interact with data through Ocean's Python library, tapping into a wealth of resources and tools. The integration of blockchain technology further ensures that AI practitioners can operate with the added security of crypto-secured data provenance.

OCEAN staking deviates from the staking models of many other cryptocurrencies. Stakers take on the role of liquidity providers, and depositing OCEAN tokens into Automated Market Maker (AMM) pools serves as a method for curating data.

What is more, the fact that datatokens are ERC-20 tokens means that they can repurpose ERC-20 wallets into data wallets, and crypto exchanges can also serve as data marketplaces. This versatility enhances the accessibility and usability of data within the Ocean Protocol ecosystem, fostering a dynamic data economy.

5. Data Cellar Marketplace Architecture Design

5.1. Overall Architecture for the Data Cellar DLT-based Marketplace

In this section, the overall architectural design (see Figure 5) for the DATA CELLAR Marketplace is presented, that describes all the components that will be developed and integrated by the end of the project.

Figure 5. Data Marketplace Architecture

5.2. Backend APIs

This component plays a crucial role in making various functionalities accessible to users via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These APIs have been constructed using the [NestJS](#) framework and are implemented in the TypeScript programming language. This ensures that the system provides a structured and efficient way for users and external systems to interact with and utilize its features and services.

5.2.1. NestJS APIs

Nest (NestJS) is a framework for building efficient, scalable [Node.js](#) server-side applications. It uses progressive JavaScript, is built with, and fully supports TypeScript (yet still enables developers to code in pure JavaScript) and combines elements of OOP (Object Oriented Programming), FP (Functional Programming), and FRP (Functional Reactive Programming).

NestJS was chosen as the backend framework for the following key motivations:

- **Built on Node.js:** NestJS is built on Node.js, a highly efficient and scalable JavaScript runtime. This means you can harness the power of JavaScript to develop the server-side of your web applications or APIs.
- **Modular Architecture:** NestJS promotes the use of a modular architecture, inspired by Angular, which organizes code into modules, each handling specific functionalities of the application. This encourages a clean, maintainable, and easily scalable structure.
- **TypeScript:** NestJS is primarily written in TypeScript, which is a superset of JavaScript with static typing. This brings the benefits of static typing to the server-side world, reducing runtime errors and improving overall code quality.
- **Decorators and Dependency Injection:** NestJS makes extensive use of decorators and dependency injection, providing an elegant way to define and inject dependencies into your backend components. This promotes decoupling and code reusability.
- **Scalability:** NestJS is highly scalable and suitable for both small applications and complex enterprise projects. Thanks to its modular architecture, you can add new modules or services without significantly altering existing code.
- **Middleware and Pipes:** NestJS provides a middleware and pipes system that allows flexible handling of HTTP requests, performing checks, authentication, data processing, and more before they reach route handlers.
- **gRPC Support:** NestJS offers native support for gRPC, a high-performance remote communication protocol, which is particularly useful for distributed applications.
- **Large Community and Documentation:** NestJS has an active community and comprehensive documentation, making learning and problem-solving easier. Additionally, it is supported by a variety of third-party modules and extensions.
- **Integration with Frontend Frameworks:** NestJS can be seamlessly integrated with frontend frameworks like Angular, enabling effortless consistency and communication between the frontend and backend.

5.3. Aquarius

[Aquarius](#) (see Figure 6), which is a pivotal component within the Ocean Protocol ecosystem, serves as a robust tool for tracking and caching metadata across various blockchains hosting the smart contracts of Ocean Protocol. Functioning off-chain and relying on an Elasticsearch database, Aquarius streamlines the querying process for on-chain generated metadata.

At its core, Aquarius plays a crucial role in monitoring the blockchain continually. It actively observes for the creation or modification of metadata, promptly recording and processing these events. This

dynamic process ensures that the database remains up to date, providing a comprehensive log of metadata activities on the blockchain.

Aquarius is not merely a passive observer; it actively contributes to the accessibility of information through its dedicated interface (API). Users can seamlessly query stored metadata, eliminating the need for manual data chain scanning. This feature-rich tool not only simplifies the process of accessing relevant information but also enhances the overall efficiency of data management within the Ocean Protocol ecosystem. Aquarius is particularly advantageous when implementing a search feature in your DApp.

Figure 6. Aquarius Ocean Protocol Component

5.3.1. Aquarius functionalities

Here are the most important features that are exhibited by Aquarius in ocean protocol:

- **Caching Mechanism:** Aquarius acts as a cache by storing metadata from multiple blockchains off-chain in an Elasticsearch database.

- **Event Monitoring:** It consistently monitors for MetadataCreated and MetadataUpdated events, processing and updating these events in the database.
- **Streamlined Query Access:** The Aquarius API offers a user-friendly method to access metadata, eliminating the need for manual blockchain scanning.
- **API Functionality:** Serving as an API, it provides a REST API that retrieves data from the off-chain datastore.
- **Events Monitoring System:** Featuring an EventsMonitor component, Aquarius runs continuously to retrieve and index chain metadata, saving the results into an Elasticsearch database.
- **Configurability:** Various components within Aquarius, such as the EventsMonitor, offer configurability. Users can customize features like the MetadataContract, Decryptor class, allowed publishers, purgatory settings, VeAllocate, start blocks, and more according to their specific needs.

5.3.2. Aquarius technologies

- **Python:** Python serves as the primary programming language within Aquarius.
- **Flask:** The Aquarius API is constructed using Flask, a Python framework.
- **Elasticsearch:** Aquarius utilizes Elasticsearch, a search and analytics engine renowned for efficient data indexing and retrieval.
- **REST API:** Aquarius adopts the REST API, a software architectural style facilitating interoperability between computer systems on the internet.

5.3.3. Aquarius integration in DATA CELLAR Data Marketplace

In the next version of the Data marketplace, the integration of Aquarius within the proposed architecture is proposed. This is because it can be an important added value in the overall health of the data marketplace, regarding:

- **Reduced Access Times:** A metadata cache speeds up access to stored data. When a user requests information already presents in the cache, response times are significantly faster compared to directly querying the blockchain. This enhances user experience, especially in situations where latency is critical.
- **Minimization of Blockchain Load:** The metadata cache helps to reduce the load on the blockchain. Much of the metadata-related requests can be handled by the cache, avoiding the need for continuous querying of the blockchain. This contributes to keeping the blockchain lighter and more responsive.
- **Efficiency in Data Updates:** A metadata cache component, like Aquarius, can continuously monitor events of metadata creation or updates on the blockchain. This ensures that the cache is always aligned with the latest information, reducing the possibility of using outdated data.
- **Overall Performance Improvement:** Using a metadata cache contributes to improving the overall performance of the data marketplace. By reducing the need for frequent interactions with the blockchain, greater efficiency and resource management are achieved.

- **Querying Ease:** The API of a metadata cache simplifies querying operations. Users can quickly obtain desired data without having to execute complex queries on the blockchain, simplifying platform usage.
- **Customization and Configurability:** A configurable metadata cache component, such as Aquarius, offers flexibility. Users can tailor the system to their needs by setting parameters like metadata contracts, Decryptor classes, and more.

However, it must be highlighted that Aquarius is a component developed specifically for the Ocean Protocol infrastructure, and it will therefore not be possible to include it in DATA CELLAR exactly as it is now. This is because Ocean protocol is only a reference for us to take as a basis for development, but which we had to heavily modify to adapt it to the needs of the project. It will therefore be essential, for successful integration, to adapt it to the data marketplace built in DATA CELLAR.

5.4. HashiCorp Vault

This component is crucial for the secure and encrypted storage and management of user information. [HashiCorp Vault](#) is a secret and sensitive data management solution that provides an infrastructure for securing data. It is designed to help organizations protect and securely manage sensitive information, such as encryption keys, passwords, access tokens, and other confidential data. Vault provides a centralized platform for secret management, allowing control over access and secure usage of this information.

The functionality it provides is fundamental for the use we need within the project:

- **Centralized Management:** Vault offers centralized secret management, enabling more precise control over access and distribution of sensitive information. This simplifies the management of private keys and other confidential data.
- **Granular Access Policies:** HashiCorp Vault allows the definition of granular access policies, specifying who has access to which resources and with what permissions. This flexibility ensures that only authorized users can access sensitive information.
- **Automatic Key Rotation:** Vault supports automatic key rotation, an essential security practice. This means that keys can be regularly changed without the need for manual intervention, reducing the risk associated with static keys.
- **Audit and Traceability:** Vault provides advanced audit features, allowing the logging of all access and modification activities to secrets. This level of traceability is crucial for compliance and security issue resolution.
- **Integration with Existing Infrastructures:** Vault is designed to integrate with various infrastructures and technologies. It can be used in conjunction with cloud services, on-premises environments, and identity management platforms, facilitating integration into existing architectures.
- **Scalable and High-Performance Architecture:** HashiCorp Vault is designed to ensure high performance and scalability. This is essential for efficiently managing large amounts of sensitive data in complex and high-usage environments.

- **Dynamic Secrets Functionality:** Vault supports dynamic secrets, allowing the creation of secrets on-demand. This feature adds a level of dynamism to key management and handling sensitive data.
- **Simplified Environment Variable Management:** Using Vault for key management can simplify the handling of environment variables, eliminating the need to store sensitive cryptographic keys in .env files.

5.5. GoQuorum and Docker environment

In the future, the use of GoQuorum for the creation of a private Ethereum network will be made possible by inserting the network nodes in special containers, through [Docker](#). This choice seems to be the best in terms of:

- **Application Isolation:** Docker allows for creating and managing containers, which are isolated environments containing all the dependencies needed to run an application. This isolation reduces conflicts between applications and simplifies deployment.
- **Ease of Distribution:** Docker containers can be consistently distributed across different platforms without worrying about configuration differences or dependencies. This significantly simplifies the deployment of the blockchain network across multiple environments.
- **Horizontal Scalability:** Docker facilitates horizontal scalability, meaning the addition of new blockchain network nodes by creating new Docker containers. This approach simplifies the management of growing blockchain networks and allows for flexible resource scaling.
- **Simplified Management:** Docker simplifies the management of blockchain nodes through the definition of configurations in Docker Compose files. This enables easy orchestration of starting, stopping, and configuring all the components necessary for the network nodes.
- **Consistent Environments:** Using Docker ensures that all blockchain network nodes run in consistent environments, reducing the possibility of errors related to configuration differences between development, testing, and production.
- **Reproducibility:** Docker allows for creating container images that can be versioned and distributed consistently. This ensures the reproducibility of environments, simplifying the management of the blockchain application lifecycle.
- **Ease of Update and Rollback:** Docker simplifies application updates and enables quick and reliable rollback to previous versions, reducing the risk of service interruptions.

5.6. PostgreSQL

[PostgreSQL](#) is an open-source, highly advanced relational database management system (RDBMS). It is designed to efficiently and reliably store, manage, and retrieve data, and has become one of the most popular and powerful databases used worldwide.

PostgreSQL is known for its features of robustness, flexibility, and scalability. It offers a wide range of advanced features, including support for transactions, data integrity, complex querying, advanced

indexing, and an extension system that allows developers to customize and extend the database to meet their specific needs.

One of PostgreSQL's distinctive features is its commitment to standards and strict adherence to the SQL standard, making it highly interoperable with other applications and databases. It is widely used in web, enterprise, and scientific applications, as well as in high-performance data processing environments.

At present, the database is primarily utilized to store and manage user wallet information within the system. Each user's wallet information includes essential details related to their digital assets, transactions, and account balances. This data is crucial for enabling secure and efficient financial transactions within the platform.

To ensure the highest level of data security, all wallet-related information is stored in an encrypted format. This encryption process involves the use of a secret key, which serves as the foundation for encrypting and decrypting the data. By employing encryption, sensitive user information is protected from unauthorized access and exposure.

The use of encryption with a secret key plays a critical role in fortifying the database's security. In the event of direct attacks or data breaches aimed at compromising the database, the encrypted data remains effectively safeguarded. Even if unauthorized parties gain access to the database, they will encounter encrypted data, making it extremely challenging to extract meaningful information without the corresponding secret key.

This approach ensures that user wallet information is shielded from potential security threats, and the use of encryption aligns with best practices for safeguarding sensitive financial data. It enhances the overall security of the system and provides users with the confidence that their wallet information is well-protected within the database.

5.7. Redis and Bull

Redis is an open-source, high-performance, in-memory data storage system. It is renowned for its speed and ability to handle large volumes of data in real-time and is often used as a key-value store or cache. Redis stands out with its in-memory data structures, going beyond simple string storage to include lists, sets, hash tables, and other complex data structures. Thanks to these features, Redis is widely used for fast data storage and retrieval in real-time applications, caching, and queue management.

Bull is a Node.js library that extends Redis for advanced queue management. Bull is ideal for handling message queues, notifications, background jobs, and other asynchronous tasks. Using Redis as a backend, Bull offers powerful features such as job prioritization, job retry in case of failure, scheduling future jobs, and distributed job management across multiple nodes. It is particularly valuable in scenarios where efficient handling of a large volume of tasks is required while ensuring system reliability and scalability.

Redis is used to create and manage message queues within the system. Each queue can represent a specific blockchain operation type, such as dataset creation, license creation, or a buy/sell dataset license. These queues serve as containers for user requests. When a user initiates an operation involving the blockchain, the request is not processed instantly but is instead placed in the

corresponding Redis queue. For example, if a user wants to create a new dataset, the request is queued in the dataset creation queue.

Bull is used to manage queues in an advanced manner. When a request is added to the queue, Bull evaluates its priority and decides whether to put it on hold by processing more important requests or to execute it immediately if the priority is high or there are no other requests in the queue. Generally, Bull handles queues in a FIFO (first in, first out) manner. Priorities can be defined for queued requests. This means that more critical or urgent transactions are given priority treatment. For instance, buy/sell transactions may have higher priority than other operations.

The proposed solution present following advantages:

- **Prevention of Network Congestion:** The Ethereum blockchain, like many other blockchain networks, can experience congestion during periods of high activity. By queuing requests using Redis and Bull, it is possible to avoid network congestion and ensure that transactions are processed smoothly and without overloads. This ensures that operations are handled efficiently, regardless of the workload on the blockchain.
- **Priority Management:** Bull allows the management of request priorities within the queue. This is particularly useful for ensuring that critical or time-sensitive transactions are processed ahead of less urgent ones.
- **Retry in Case of Errors:** Bull supports the retry of requests in case of errors. This means that if a transaction were to fail, it will be requeued for a new attempt. This enhances the system's resilience and reduces the risk of losing important operations.
- **Monitoring and Reporting:** Redis and Bull also provide advanced monitoring and reporting tools. These tools allow tracking of queued operations, monitoring their status, and identifying any issues. This data can be valuable for optimization and issue resolution.
- **Scalability and Distribution:** Redis and Bull are highly scalable and support distribution across multiple nodes, enabling the system to grow as needed without sacrificing performance.
- **Improved User Experience:** This solution ensures a better user experience as transactions are consistently and reliably managed, avoiding delays or errors due to network congestion.

5.8. Overall Architecture for the DLT-based Marketplace Version 1

In this chapter, a preview of the architecture of the first prototype of our blockchain-based data marketplace will be presented. This initial prototype is designed to provide an overview of basic functionalities and fundamental principles of the platform, with an imminent release that will make available only selected functionalities.

Figure 7. DLT-based Data Marketplace Reduced Architecture for Preliminary Prototype (M18)

Figure above illustrates the schematic architecture of our first prototype. This prototype has been designed to demonstrate a limited selection of key functionalities, offering a preliminary view of the platform's potential.

The prototype focuses on:

- **Blockchain Layer:** Using a blockchain as the foundation, data management and security mechanisms will be implemented to ensure data integrity, allowing secure and verifiable transactions.
- **Simplified Backend Operations:** A backend framework will be operational for foundational data transactions and integrity maintenance. Initially, only basic data handling functionalities will be accessible.

- **Limited Features:** This initial prototype will offer a subset of functionalities of the complete data marketplace, focusing on basic data viewing and minimal data sharing operations.

It is anticipated that this initial prototype will serve as an early preview of the complete functionalities of the data marketplace. Further iterations and developments will enable a gradual enrichment of the platform to include a wide array of advanced features and a comprehensive user experience.

The release of this initial prototype will represent a significant step toward the realization of a complete and functional blockchain-based data marketplace, outlining the pathway for its further evolution.

5.9. Ganache

In the implementation of this preliminary prototype, [Ganache](#) will be used to test the functionality of the marketplace in a controlled blockchain environment. Ganache is an Ethereum development environment that provides a local, private, and simulated Ethereum blockchain. It is one of the components of Truffle, a popular framework for smart contract and DApp development on Ethereum. Ganache is primarily designed for development and testing purposes and offers many useful features:

- **Local Blockchain:** Ganache creates a local Ethereum blockchain on computer, completely isolated from the main Ethereum network. This means it is possible to test and develop private blockchain applications without performing real transactions on the Ethereum network, avoiding real costs and risks.
- **Pre-generated Accounts and Balances:** Ganache provides a set of pre-generated Ethereum accounts with virtual ether. This makes it easy to simulate interactions between users and smart contracts without worrying about obtaining actual ether from the main network.
- **Speed and Control:** It is possible to control the behavior of the local blockchain, speeding up or slowing down blocks, adding custom smart contracts, and simulating specific scenarios. This allows to thoroughly test private blockchain application in a controlled environment.
- **Integration with Development Tools:** Ganache integrates well with a variety of development tools, including Truffle, Remix, and MetaMask, simplifying the development and testing process for smart contracts and DApps.
- **Easy Customization:** Ganache allows for straightforward customization. It is easy configure and adapt the blockchain to meet the specific requirements of specific project, making it an ideal choice for tailoring the environment to specific prototype's needs. Below, some specific parameters that can be modified based on personal needs are presented:
 - **Number of Accounts:** You can specify the number of Ethereum accounts available in the blockchain. This allows to simulate a specific user base or network size.
 - **Account Balances:** Ganache allows to set the initial ether balances for each account, so it is possible to control the distribution of virtual funds among simulated users.
 - **Gas Prices:** It is possible to customize gas prices for transactions to simulate different network conditions or to control the cost of executing smart contracts.
 - **Block Times:** Ganache allows to adjust block time intervals. This can help to simulate a faster or slower blockchain, which is useful for testing time-dependent functionalities in smart contracts.

- **Hard Fork Configuration:** It is possible to select which Ethereum hard fork or network upgrade to mimic in the blockchain. This is crucial for compatibility testing when Ethereum undergoes protocol changes.
- **Network ID:** It is possible to set a custom network ID to differentiate the private blockchain from the main Ethereum network. This is essential when configuring Ethereum clients and tools to connect to Ganache instance.
- **EVM (Ethereum Virtual Machine) Configuration:** Ganache supports custom EVM configurations, allowing to fine-tune the behavior of the virtual machine to match project's requirements.
- **Mining Settings:** It is possible to control how quickly new blocks are mined, including block interval and difficulty. This can help to simulate different mining scenarios.
- **Chain State and Data:** Ganache provides options to preload the blockchain with specific data, such as initial contract states, balances, and transactions. This is valuable for replicating real-world scenarios.
- **Forking from Mainnet:** It is possible to fork Ganache instance from the Ethereum Mainnet at a specific block number. This enables to interact with the Mainnet state while conducting local development and testing.
- **Custom Events:** It is possible to generate custom events and log messages in smart contracts to mimic various scenarios and test event handling in your DApp.
- **Account Mnemonics and Keys:** Ganache allows to set custom account mnemonics or private keys for specific accounts, enabling to control access to accounts with known private keys for testing purposes.
- **Custom Contract Deployments:** It is possible to deploy smart contracts to the Ganache blockchain, which is essential for testing the functionality of your specific contracts.

Ganache is a good choice for the initial development phase of the first prototype of the marketplace for several reasons:

- **Development Speed:** Because Ganache offers a local development environment, you can develop and test quickly without waiting for block confirmations on the main network. These speeds up the development process.
- **Cost Reduction:** Operating on a local blockchain with virtual ether means you do not have to worry about real transaction costs on Ethereum. This allows you to experiment and iterate on your idea without spending real ether.
- **Total Control:** You have full control over the local blockchain, enabling you to simulate complex scenarios, verify the functionality of your smart contracts, and resolve any issues without interfering with the main Ethereum network.
- **Security:** Using Ganache eliminates the risk of costly errors during the initial development. You can test your smart contract in a secure environment before deploying it to the main blockchain.

5.9.1. Actual customize configuration

Currently, the private blockchain built through Ganache has been initialized as follows:

- Immutable set of user wallets, i.e., public address and private key pairs with a balance equal to 1000 ETH, as they are generated through the same passphrase. This turns out to be vital to enable the disbursement of money toward new users who sign up for the first time on the given DATA CELLAR platform.
- Gas-limit set to a higher value: "Gas" is a unit of measurement for the use of computational resources on the blockchain. Every operation or computation performed on a blockchain requires a certain amount of gas to be completed. This gas is used to cover the costs of executing operations and to ensure that the network is not congested by complex or infinite transactions. The "gas limit" represents the maximum number of gas units that a user is willing to spend for the execution of a transaction. In other words, it is an upper limit on the gas consumption for a particular transaction. When you send a transaction on a blockchain, you need to specify a value for the gas limit.
- The gas limit is a measure of how much computational work the blockchain network must perform to process your transaction. The more complex the transaction (e.g., executing a complex smart contract), the more gas is required. If the gas limit set in your transaction is too low to cover the required work, the transaction may not be successfully completed and will be cancelled, but the gas spent will still be consumed. For this initial approach gas limit was incremented to permit to correctly execute smart contract interactions.
- Local storage of Blockchain History: Since the blockchain is running locally, the moment it is turned off all history up to that point is lost. For this reason, a local persistence of the data is created so that everything is not lost every time it is turned back on to run smart contract tests or other.

5.10. Smart contract and token design

Figure 8. Smart contract configuration

DATA CELLAR smart contracts (see Figure 8) are written in Solidity, which is the main language for writing smart contracts for Ethereum-based blockchains. Solidity was chosen for several reasons:

- **Designed specifically for smart contracts:** Solidity was developed specifically for writing smart contracts on Ethereum. This means that the language was designed with the peculiarities of the Ethereum blockchain and the needs of smart contracts in mind.
- **Popularity and widespread adoption:** Solidity is widely used in the Ethereum developer community and is supported by a wide range of tools and resources. Its popularity makes it easier to find resources, libraries, and experienced developers to help with the creation and auditing of smart contracts.
- **Security:** Solidity places a particular emphasis on the security of smart contracts. It has constructs that help prevent common errors, such as integer overflow or unintended operations. However, security also depends on the developer's expertise, and Solidity provides tools to mitigate many risks.

- **Ease of use:** Solidity was designed to be relatively easy to learn for programmers familiar with languages like JavaScript or C++. This makes it easier for developers to adopt and use.
- **Ethereum support:** As the official smart contract language of Ethereum, Solidity is well-supported by the Ethereum platform itself. Ethereum developers are constantly working on improvements and updates for Solidity.
- **Ecosystem and community:** Solidity is part of a vast ecosystem of developers, auditors, development tools, and educational resources. This facilitates connecting with the community and accessing learning resources.

Furthermore, it should be specified that these smart contracts have taken as their logic those developed in the Ocean Protocol project. This is because, based on the benchmark analysis, it was identified as the best data marketplace based on the KPIs analysed.

Data NFT Factory

This is the contract responsible for the creation of digitised data through the instantiation of Data NFT template smart contract and the purchase of associated licences using the [Balancer](#) functionalities. Furthermore, to give users absolute control over their data, data deletion functionalities have been implemented. In this way, at any time, energy data owners can remove the data from the blockchain.

Data NFT Template

This contract represents the digitised energy dataset in the form of NFT through the implementation of [ERC721](#) standard. Within the contract will be a set of information about the dataset and the link between the NFT and the raw (real) data in the dataspace. The contract will make available to the owner of the dataset the possibility of creating licences associated with it to make the dataset usable for other users interested in its use.

Datatoken Template

It represents a specific license associated with an NFT through the implementation of [ERC20](#) standard. Each NFT can be associated with multiple licences with different characteristics that can be customised by the creator of the licence, i.e., the owner of the energy dataset. Users who want to use a dataset will then have to buy a token of the licence with which they want to use the dataset. Buying and selling will allow the exchange of the currency defined in [DATA CELLAR Token contract](#) for the licence token. The exchange value will be defined in the licence itself.

Data Cellar Token

The contract defines the main currency of the entire ecosystem with which the exchange of assets within the blockchain will take place. This is through the implementation, again, of the [ERC20](#) standard. All licences associated with a certain NFT will have an association between their cost in terms of DATA CELLAR Token.

Balancer

This contract deals on a practical level with the actual exchange, between the parties involved in a transaction, of specific assets. Specifically, it allows the transfer of DATA CELLAR Tokens from the buyer's wallet to the seller's wallet and of datatokens from the wallet of the owner of the relevant

dataset to the buyer's wallet. The functionality that this contract provides can only be triggered by the Data NFT Factory. This is to make the infrastructure more secure and prevent malicious users from exploiting possible vulnerabilities.

5.11. Available functionalities

The following functionalities were made available for this first prototype:

- **User Registration:** When a user registers on the DATA CELLAR platform, the backend takes care of generating a unique set of a public address and a private key associated with the user's account. This process ensures a secure and personalized digital identity for each user. The public address serves as a unique pseudonym within our system, enabling secure and traceable transactions on the Ethereum blockchain.
- **Wallet Initialization:** In addition to assigning a unique identifier, the backend also allocates an initial balance of DATA CELLAR Tokens (DCT) to the wallet of the newly registered user. This initial balance provides users with the ability to actively participate in transactions within our marketplace without the need to acquire cryptocurrencies beforehand. DATA CELLAR Tokens serve as the currency within our ecosystem, allowing users to access goods and services within the marketplace.
- **Viewing Available Datasets:** Users can access a comprehensive listing of all available energy datasets within the platform. These datasets are open for purchase through associated licenses. This feature enables users to explore the wide range of energy-related data available in the marketplace and make informed decisions about which datasets and associated licenses they would like to acquire. It provides transparency and visibility into the energy data offerings within the platform.
- **Viewing Personal Data and Licenses:** Users can access a detailed list of all the data and licenses they own personally. This includes datasets and licenses created by the user. It provides a convenient way for users to keep track of their personally owned data and licenses.
- **Viewing Purchased Data and Licenses:** Users can also view a comprehensive list of all the data and licenses they have purchased and, as a result, could use at any time. This feature ensures users have visibility into the data and licenses they have acquired within the platform.
- **Creating Datasets and Associated Licenses:** Users have the capability to create their datasets and the licenses linked to them. This empowers users to contribute their data to the marketplace, establish their licensing terms, and share their data with other users, thereby enriching the overall ecosystem with new content.
- **Data and License Deletion:** Users can delete their datasets and associated licenses from the blockchain at any time. This feature grants users the highest level of control over their information. It allows users to manage and remove their data and licenses when needed, ensuring their data remains in their control and can be withdrawn from the platform as desired. This empowers users to maintain their privacy and data autonomy within the marketplace.

It is important to emphasise that users do not have control of their wallets but are directly managed by the backend in a completely transparent manner for end users. This choice is based on a number of positive aspects listed below:

- **Simplification for Users:** End-users often find the technical management of wallets and private keys to be complex and risky. A centralized and transparent implementation significantly simplifies the user experience, as users do not need to worry about the technical management of their wallets. This makes the platform more accessible and user-friendly.
- **Enhanced Security:** Centralized wallet management allows for the implementation of advanced security procedures. The backend can monitor and respond to potential threats, providing an extra level of protection. This can help reduce the risks of theft or loss of funds due to human errors or cyberattacks.
- **User Assistance:** In case a user encounters issues with their wallet, the support team can aid more effectively since they have direct access to wallet details. This reduces downtime and potential user frustrations.
- **Compliance and Regulations:** Centralized management can simplify regulatory compliance. The backend can implement user verification and identification procedures to ensure compliance with regulations, such as anti-money laundering (AML) and know your customer (KYC) requirements.
- **Monitoring and Reporting:** The backend can track user activities in a detailed manner, facilitating report generation and trend analysis. This data can be valuable for optimizing services, detecting anomalies, and improving the user experience.
- **Reduced User Workload:** Automatic wallet management allows users to focus on their activities within the platform, without the need to manually manage wallet details. This can increase convenience and platform adoption.

6. Conclusions

The goal of this document is to report on activities performed in T6.2 including the benchmark of existing Data Marketplace solutions, the selection of the best approach for DATA CELLAR and the design of a target DLT-based Architecture to be adopted in DATA CELLAR together with a preliminary implementation of the main subcomponents and functionalities.

The benchmark analysis, based on a set of specific Key Performance Indicators, identified Ethereum and Ocean Protocol as the best tool to build the DLT-based Marketplace and a preliminary version of the architectural components of the marketplace and related functionalities was demonstrated by Task 6.2 participants and validated by the entire DATA CELLAR consortium.

This work will continue in the scope of the Task 6.3 and T6.5, where the DLT-Marketplace will be further implemented, enriched with new functionalities, and integrated with the rest of DATA CELLAR platform.

In the second version of the Deliverable D6.3 - "DLT Architecture and Governance Model – Issue 2", which will take place in month 36, an improved and final solution will be proposed regarding the implementation of the DLT Data Marketplace.